

UNIVERSIDAD DE LOS
PUEBLOS DE EUROPA

ELABORATION AND SUBSEQUENT APPLICATION OF A PROTOCOL FOR MEASURE REDUCTION IN A PATIENT WITH HASHIMOTO THYROIDITIS

SARA GARCIA DIOGO GONÇALVES

Thesis to obtain Master degree

Master of Aesthetic and Anti-Aging Medicine of the Universidad de los
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“...Then God said: “Let us make man in our image, according to our likeness...”

Genesis 1:26

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Abbreviations

% - percentage

AD – Autoimmune Disease

BMI – Body Mass Index

CD – Celiac Disease

cm – centimeter

Kg – kilogram

KJ – kilojoule

RF - Radiofrequency

Abstract

Hypothyroidism is the result of insufficient production or absence of production of thyroid hormones, which may be congenital or acquired.

Chronic autoimmune thyroiditis is the leading cause of hypothyroidism in countries where diet provides a sufficient supply of iodine. The incidence of this thyroiditis has increased exponentially over the last 50 years, which may be related to the increase in iodine content in the diet.

Due to the insidious evolution of the disease, the doctor will find patients with less specific complaints, such as: weight gain (moderate), intestinal constipation or sensation of paresthesia.

In this thesis, potential triggers of autoimmune thyroid disease are analyzed and thus, a list of foods that can be consumed and those that need to be avoided.

Additionally, and based on the diet, a protocol for the reduction of measures for a Hashimoto thyroiditis patient was performed and the results obtained were analyzed.

Anatomy of the Thyroid

The thyroid gland is located in the lower third of the neck, immediately below the larynx, lining the anterior part of the trachea, at the level of the C5 - T1 vertebrae. It is located between the sternothyroid and sternohyoid muscles. It is a very vascularized organ, supplied by the superior and inferior thyroid arteries, and drained by the thyroid venous plexus constituted by the superior, middle and inferior thyroid veins. The thyroid nerves are derivative from the upper, middle, and lower cervical sympathetic ganglia. The endocrine secretion of this gland is hormonally controlled by the hypothalamus-hypophysis-thyroid axis. Its shape resembles a butterfly because it consists of two lateral lobes, each about 4 to 6 cm long, 1.5 cm wide and 2 to 3 cm thick, located on both sides of the trachea and united by a narrow piece of tissue, called the isthmus. In some individuals, the gland also has a small extension in the upper part, called the pyramidal lobe. Under normal conditions, although it is very superficial, the thyroid is not palpable.

Figure 1- Anatomy of the Thyroid. Adapted from (Davis 2016)

Hypothyroidism

Hypothyroidism is the result of insufficient production or absence of production of thyroid hormones, which may be congenital or acquired. Screening for congenital hypothyroidism makes the severity of its consequences, if not corrected early, part of the research on metabolic diseases of the "test of the foot." The objective is to detect this anomaly before the clinical manifestation of the disease so it is possible to start the

therapy immediately. The most frequent causes of primary acquired hypothyroidism are: total or partial surgical removal of the thyroid gland (total or partial thyroidectomy), autoimmune thyroiditis such as Hashimoto's disease and treatments with radioactive iodine. Secondary hypothyroidism may occur due to: pituitary dysfunction or excess iodine and may be induced by some medications such as lithium, interferon and anti-thyroid drugs. (Grandjean and Aubry 2009)

The term thyroiditis describes a set of processes that occur with inflammation of the thyroid gland (Table 1). If in some cases, the etiology is well known, for example in acute thyroiditis in which a bacterial infection is involved or in chronic autoimmune thyroiditis whose origin is in an autoimmune process, some doubts remain about the etiology of other pictures. Autoimmune thyroiditis is a chronic autoimmune thyroiditis, often referred to as chronic lymphocytic thyroiditis or Hashimoto's thyroiditis, postpartum thyroiditis, and painless sporadic thyroiditis. (Pearce, Farwell et al. 2003)

Type	Synonyms
Chronic autoimmune thyroiditis	Chronic lymphocytic thyroiditis Hashimoto's Thyroiditis
Postpartum thyroiditis	Painless postpartum thyroiditis
Painless sporadic thyroiditis	Silent sporadic thyroiditis Subacute lymphocytic thyroiditis
Subacute thyroiditis	Quervain's thyroiditis Giant cell thyroiditis Subacute granulomatous thyroiditis Pseudo granulomatous thyroiditis
Acute thyroiditis	Suppurated thyroiditis Pyogenic thyroiditis Infectious thyroiditis Bacterial thyroiditis
Drug-Induced Thyroiditis	
Riedel Thyroiditis	Fibrous Thyroiditis

Table 1- Types of Thyroiditis. Adapted from (Pearce, Farwell et al. 2003)

Autoimmune thyroid disease is a common pathology. In the United States of America, it is estimated that 10% of the population has antibodies against

thyroid antigens. (Tunbridge, Evered et al. 1977) This prevalence is higher in the white race, where it reaches 14%, and lower in the black race, where it reaches 5%. (Hollowell, Staehling et al. 2002) The prevalence is also higher in the female sex, with a female / male sex ratio of 8-9: 1, and increases with age; about 25% of women over the age of 60 have anti - thyroid antibodies. Most people with detectable anti-thyroid antibodies have normal glandular function. However, chronic autoimmune thyroiditis is the leading cause of hypothyroidism in countries where diet provides a sufficient supply of iodine.

Hashimoto thyroiditis

Chronic autoimmune thyroiditis is the most frequent thyroiditis and is the most common cause of goiter and hypothyroidism in countries where diet provides a sufficient supply of iodine. It is considered a classic example of organ-specific autoimmune disease. It is also called chronic lymphocytic thyroiditis or Hashimoto's thyroiditis. (Slatosky, Shipton et al. 2000)

Up to 95% of cases occur in women. (Slatosky, Shipton et al. 2000) It affects people of all ages, especially those in their 30s and 50s. The incidence of this thyroiditis has increased exponentially over the last 50 years, which may be related to the increase in iodine content in the diet. (Slatosky, Shipton et al. 2000) The prevalence and cumulative incidence of subclinical hypothyroidism and autoimmune thyroiditis increases with increasing iodine intake. (Teng, Shan et al. 2006)

The designation of Hashimoto's thyroiditis is due to Hashimoto, referring to patients with goiter and intense lymphocytic thyroid infiltration ("struma lymphomatosa"). Some clinicians reserve this designation for patients with goiter and hypothyroidism. However, many patients do not present hypothyroidism and others do not present goiter and can present atrophic thyroid. These are considered manifestations of the same disease with different clinical phenotypes.

The natural course of the disease is the gradual loss of thyroid function. Among patients with this condition who exhibit moderate increases in TSH and in the presence of anti-thyroid antibodies, hypothyroidism occurs at a rate of 5% per year. (Vanderpump, Tunbridge et al. 1995)

The main clinical manifestations are the signs and symptoms of hypothyroidism. Very rarely hyper alternation and hypothyroidism may occur due to the intermittent presence of stimulatory and blocking antibodies. (Pearce, Farwell et al. 2003)

Due to the insidious evolution of the disease, the doctor will find patients with less specific complaints, such as: weight gain (moderate), intestinal constipation or sensation of paresthesia. (Table 2)

Most Common Symptoms Related to Hypothyroidism
Decreased sweating
Hoarseness
Paresthesia
Dry skin
Intestinal constipation
Decreased hearing acuity
Weight gain

Table 2- Most Common Symptoms Related to Hypothyroidism. Adapted from (Silva 2011)

Nutrition

Nutrition has increasingly played a relevant role both in development and in altering the course of autoimmune diseases (AD). Nutritional status is very important for the balance of the immune system and, from an early age, the incidence of specific diseases with local nutritional deficiencies was related. However, the specific connection between dietary factors and the initiation or modulation of AD is a more recent and still poorly understood acquisition. (Selmi and Tsuneyama 2010)

Adequate feeding may be a key factor in improving the prognosis of AD, as it can help prevent infections and the progression of associated comorbidities (e.g. cardiovascular and metabolic diseases), as well as reduce the impact of iatrogenic in certain treatments (e.g. changes in lipid profile due to corticosteroid use). On the other hand, several lines of evidence support the use of specific dietary factors to improve the course of the disease (e.g. vitamin D, probiotics, flavonoids) (Selmi and Tsuneyama 2010)

Potential Triggers of Autoimmune Disease

Gluten

It is estimated that 2-7% of patients with autoimmune thyroid disease (Graves' disease and Hashimoto's thyroiditis) have Celiac Disease (CD), which is the autoimmune pathology most commonly associated with autoimmune thyroid disease. (Denham and Hill 2013, Lauret and Rodrigo 2013) The inverse has also been described; Up to 26% of celiac patients have positive serology for autoimmune thyroid disease, and thyroid dysfunction has been detected in 10% of cases. Celiac patients are estimated to have a 3-fold higher risk for the disease in the control group. (Lauret and Rodrigo 2013) However, a gluten-free diet does not hinder the progress of the autoimmune process. (Metso, Hyytia-Ilmonen et al. 2012)

Salt

Increased dietary salt intake may represent an environmental risk factor for the development of AD in susceptible individuals through the induction of the pathogenic phenotype of Th17 cells. (Klenewietfeld, Manzel et al. 2013)

Selenium

Selenium is a trace element with a significant role in multiple reactions, particularly in regard to maintaining oxidation balance. Selenium deficiency, through the induction of a state of oxidative stress, may be related to the pathogenesis of multiple diseases, by mechanisms still unclear.

Selenium interference in the regulation of immunity may also contribute to the relationship between this element and the genesis of autoimmune pathology. It is important to note the special relationship that selenium has with thyroid physiology, both in terms of its normal functioning and with the sequences of events that lead to goiter formation, thyroid neoplasia or autoimmune thyroid pathology. Clinical trials involving selenium supplementation in subjects with autoimmune thyroiditis and Graves' disease have shown significant benefit at the analytical, imaging, and, to a lesser extent, clinical level after 6 months. Selenium supplementation will be particularly advantageous in women with autoimmune thyroiditis who wish to become pregnant regardless of whether they belong to a population with adequate selenium intakes and are likely to decrease the risk of thyroid dysfunction during that period. (Esteves, Neves et al. 2012)

Zinc

There are reports in the literature that zinc deficiency is a cause of subclinical hypothyroidism. (Betsy, Binitha et al. 2013) In animal studies, zinc deficiency resulted in approximately 30% decrease in free T3 and T4 levels. (Kelly 2000)

In humans, zinc supplementation restored normal thyroid function in patients with hypothyroidism. In the study by Nishiyama et al. (Nishiyama, Futagoishi-Suginohara et al. 1994), supplementation of zinc sulphate was performed in subjects with low T3, normal free T4 and moderate zinc deficiency for 12 months. Oral supplementation decreased serum levels of free T3 and T3 and rT3, and HRT induced TSH reaction normalized.

Soy

According to Messina and Redmond (Messina and Redmond 2006), the literature provides little evidence that euthyroid subjects without iodine deficiency have adverse effects on soy foods or isoflavones. However, there is a theoretical concern based on in vitro and animal studies that individuals with compromised thyroid function and / or whose iodine intake is marginal may increase the risk of developing hypothyroidism with soy consumption. Therefore, it is important for consumers of soy-based foods to make sure their intake of iodine is adequate.

In addition, soybeans can block the absorption of thyroid drugs. (Messina and Redmond 2006) Thus, individuals with high soy consumption should be monitored and new research into the harmful effects and benefits of soybeans on thyroid hormones is required.

Iodine

Iodine is the essential element for the synthesis of thyroid hormones, in addition to being essential for growth and development, particularly the brain and central nervous system. (Pearce 2014) Its deficiency is a global public health problem, affecting about 800 million people. (Triggiani, Tafaro et al. 2009)

Mezzomo (Mezzomo 2016) mentions that iodine plays a key role in the production of thyroid hormones. Excessive or deficit amounts of iodine contribute to thyroid changes, including hypothyroidism.

Aesthetic Medicine Treatments

There are countless treatments used in Aesthetic Medicine to elaborate a measure reduction protocol.

Radiofrequency

Radiofrequency (RF) is a noninvasive modality capable of stimulating changes in collagen conformation and inducing neocollagenesis by generating thermal energy in a controlled manner in deep layers of cutaneous and subcutaneous tissue.

The researched references demonstrated that the use of RF for the treatment of flaccidity causes changes in collagen fibers being visible through the improvement of skin tonicity reducing wrinkling and sagging. Different studies have shown that at least eight sessions are needed once a week to achieve a satisfactory result. During and after treatment with RF, sports practice routines and a healthy diet are necessary.

Carvalho (Carvalho 2011) performed an analysis in rats that suggests that at a frequency of treatment of at least seven days, the permanence of RF effects in the collagen tissue is up to 15 days, though moderate temperatures of 37°C to 39 °C improve the condition of the tissues, conducive to neoformation of collagen and appearance of high amount of subepithelial vessels.

The contraindications of radiofrequency are:

- Cancer
- Pregnant or breastfeed
- Coagulopathies
- Neuromuscular or connective tissue disorders (lupus, erythema butterfly, ...)
- Pacemaker or metal prostheses in the area to be treated
- Cardiovascular diseases
- Recent Collagen Injections
- Fever
- Uncontrolled Diabetes
- Infections in the area to be treated
- Epilepsy

Cavitation

The term cavitation means cavity formation in an organism. In the case of aesthetic medicine cavitation, a low frequency ultrasound technology (30 to 70 KHz) is used, which causes the formation of microbubbles in adipose tissue. The adipocytes inflate until they eventually implode, forming the aforementioned "cavities". (V. Rapallini)

With the fragmentation of the fat cells, the content of these cells is released and absorbed by the lymphatic system that will have as mission to get rid of it. This time the fat content, called triglycerides, is not in danger of getting into the bloodstream and will be eliminated from the body in the same way as when eating a high-fat meal.

The contraindications of cavitation are:

- Allergy to ceramics or other components
- Pregnant or breast-feeding
- Treatment of tumors
- Contagious diseases
- Autoimmune diseases
- Uncontrolled cholesterol
- Phlebitis (inflammation in the veins)
- Pacemaker or implanted electrodes
- Circulatory problems or hypertension
- Features of skin.

Side effects are:

- Small bruises

Mesotherapy

Mesotherapy is the technique through which subcutaneous or intradermal microinjections, dermaroller or by electroporation, are introduced only and exclusively in the area to be treated.

The contraindications are:

- Pregnancy
- Breast-feeding
- Dermatological problems
- Diabetes
- Steroid or hormonal therapy

- Heart problems
- Deficiency in thyroid hormone
- Oncologic disease
- Renal insufficiency.
- Uncontrolled cholesterol and triglycerides
- Allergy to some compound

Electrostimulation

This is a procedure that uses electric currents for various purposes, among them the treatment of tissue flaccidity, muscle toning and lymphatic drainage. It is also possible to use the stimulation for a special treatment, in which the device is programmed for multiple actions and thus, a little of each treatment is obtained.

Electrostimulation causes muscle contraction, increasing blood circulation, improving cell oxygenation and eliminating toxins.

This procedure improves blood flow and lymphatic flow, treats cellulite, localized fat, and post-traumatic, acute and chronic edema.

The contraindications are:

- Congestive heart disease
- Pacemaker
- Circulatory diseases such as phlebitis, emboli, varicose veins, thrombophlebitis
- Pregnancy
- Hypertension
- Inflammatory processes
- Neoplasia
- Chronic kidney problems
- Pulmonary diseases such as emphysema
- Skin Tattoos
- Infectious diseases
- Inflammatory rheumatism
- Cardiac insufficiency
- Fever.

Cryotherapy

Cryotherapy is a technique that consists in cooling the tissue by increasing the basal metabolism with intuition of the body to cause an increase in body temperature. (Meyer 2003)

According to Guiro, (GUIRRO 1998) cryotherapy can also be applied by means of bandages consisting of the application of cryotherapeutic gel, followed by the placement of bandages soaked in camphor and menthol solution, which assists in the temperature drop by evaporation. Bandaging in addition to improving the quality of cooling keeps you longer.

The body will produce more heat to compensate for its loss by evaporation and driving, this will increase the local metabolic rate. The use of local cold acts by the conduction mechanism leading to body heat and bringing the cold, as the heat moves by looking for an internal and external temperature balance. Thus thermoregulation causes the stimulation necessary for the lipolysis of the adipose tissue of the cooled place to take place, in order to reheat it, the fat volume will decrease. (SIMONATO 2013)

The contraindications are:

- Infectious diseases
- Hypertension and previous stroke
- Skin infections
- Diabetes
- After mealtime
- Intolerance or hypersensitivity to cold
- Coagulopathies
- After surgery
- Kidney problems
- Rheumatic problems
- Heart diseases
- Cancer
- Obese individuals are not advised to do this technique because it only fights localized fat, not overweight.

Pressuretherapy

Pressuretherapy is based on a computer-controlled mechanical compression system, which is operated with the use of blow-up pumps. The apparatus has five separate chambers, which are placed around the limbs. These focus on

moving the venous and lymphatic flow from the ankles, progressively increasing to the upper thighs. As it is designed to increase blood circulation and lymphatic flow, it achieves an increase in the clearance of cellular fluid.

The contraindications are:

- Deep vein thrombosis
- Presence of pain or numbness
- Infection in the treated area
- Heart diseases
- Use in the abdomen in pregnant women
- Oncologic disease
- Renal insufficiency
- Medication to increase venous and/or lymphatic flow

Side effects are a possible mark of the device.

Treatment procedures

Elaboration of the food plan

The elaboration of the alimentary plan passed by the survey of foods that can be consumed and those that will have to be avoided, based on the analysis of the potential triggers of AD (Table 3).

Consume	Avoid
Almonds Asparagus Bean Beef Brewer's yeast Canned tuna Carrot Chicken meat Cockle Cooked shrimp with no sauces Corn Cucumber Dark bread Dried seaweed Egg yolk Garlic Lactose-free Yoghurts Lettuce Lobster Orange Oysters Pasta and brown rice Peanuts Plowing Pork liver Prunes Pumpkin Quinoa Saltwater fish Strawberries Sunflower seeds Walnuts	Caffeine Flax seeds Green tea Lactose Pasta, rice, bread (based on wheat) Raw vegetables: cabbage, corn, broccoli, Brussels sprouts, cauliflower and spinach Soy and Derivatives Sugar consumption Sweet potato
Physical activity is indicated in the treatment of hypothyroidism, mainly due to the difficulty of losing and maintaining weight	

Table 3 - Foods that can be consumed and those that will have to be avoided based on the analysis of the potential triggers of Autoimmune Diseases.

Measures reduction protocol

The area chosen for the reduction of measurements was the abdomen. There will be 12 sessions that will be distributed as follows:

	Procedure	Protocol
Session 1	Cavitation + Pressuretherapy	20 min of Cavitation + 30 min of Pressuretherapy
Session 2	Radiofrequency	20 min
Session 3	Pressuretherapy + Cryotherapy	Gel with cold effect on the abdomen + 30 min of Pressuretherapy
Session 4	Electrostimulation + Massage	25 min of Electrostimulation in the abdominal area. Immediately afterwards a modeling massage
Session 5	Cavitation + Pressuretherapy	20 min of Cavitation + 30 min of Pressuretherapy
Session 6	Radiofrequency	20 min
Session 7	Cavitation + Pressuretherapy	20 min of Cavitation + 30 min of Pressuretherapy
Session 8	Radiofrequency	20 min
Session 9	Electrostimulation + Massage	25 min of Electrostimulation in the abdominal area. Immediately afterwards a modeling massage
Session 10	Cavitation + Pressuretherapy	20 min of Cavitation + 30 min of Pressuretherapy
Session 11	Pressuretherapy + Cryotherapy	Gel with cold effect on the abdomen + 30 min of Pressuretherapy
Session 12	Radiofrequency	20 min

Table 4 - Protocol of reduction of measures - abdomen

Initial consultation and evaluation

The initial consultation and subsequent treatments were developed in Clínica Áurea – Clínica de Biomedicina Estética, localized in Rua de Três Lagares, bloco 1, loja G, Quinta da Redonda, Mateus, 5000-577 Vila Real.

In the initial consultation, all the procedures that were to be performed were explained, as well as side effects, expected results and contraindications.

The patient signed informed consent.

It is a female patient of 26 years of age. Initial weight of 63.1 kg and a height of 160 cm. Body mass index (BMI) of 24.6.

It presents hyperlipodystrophy in the abdominal area and thighs and cellulitis in the thigh area.

In the initial consultation, the following measures were also taken (Table 5), which will serve as a reference for each treatment session and to be able to evaluate the result.

Weight (Kg)	%Fat mass	%Water	Visceral fat	Muscle mass (Kg)	Basal Mean Index (KJ)	
63,1	30,9	48,7	3	41,4	1349	
Abdomen (cm)	Waist (cm)	5 cm below belly button (cm)	Right thigh (cm)	Left thigh (cm)	Right arm (cm)	Left arm (cm)
88	77	101	60	61	32	32

Table 5 - Table used for the measurements

The initial photos were taken.

Figure 2 - Initial photos: a) frontal; b) left lateral

The patient reported that she did not want to perform Mesotherapy treatments, because she reported that she had already done it in the past and that it had been quite painful.

Although the area being evaluated was the abdomen, a thigh protocol was also performed:

	Treatment	Protocol
Session 1	Pressuretherapy	30 min
Session 2	Pressuretherapy + Cryotherapy	Gel with cold effect on the abdomen + 30 min of Pressuretherapy
Session 3	Radiofrequency	15 min in each zone (right front leg, right back leg, left front leg, left back leg)
Session 4	Pressuretherapy + Cryotherapy	Gel with cold effect on the abdomen + 30 min of Pressuretherapy
Session 5	Pressuretherapy	30 min
Session 6	Radiofrequency	20 min
Session 7	Electrostimulation + Massage	25 min of Electrostimulation. Immediately afterwards a modeling massage
Session 8	Pressuretherapy	30 min
Session 9	Pressuretherapy + Cryotherapy	Gel with cold effect on the abdomen + 30 min of Pressuretherapy
Session 10	Pressuretherapy + Cryotherapy	Gel with cold effect on the abdomen + 30 min of Pressuretherapy
Session 11	Radiofrequency	15 min in each zone (right front leg, right back leg, left front leg, left back leg)
Session 12	Electrostimulation + Massage	25 min of Electrostimulation. Immediately afterwards a modeling massage

Table 6 - Measures reduction protocol - thighs

Results

After the 12 treatment sessions, the results are as follows:

Date	Weight (Kg)	%Fat mass	%Water	Visceral fat	Muscle mass (Kg)	Basal Mean Index (KJ)
01/08/2017	63,1	30,9	48,7	3	41,4	1349
03/08/2017	63,1	30,4	49,0	3	41,7	1355
08/08/2017	61,8	28,8	50,1	2	41,8	1353
11/08/2017	62,6	31,1	48,4	3	40,9	1337
15/08/2017	62,4	32,2	47,6	3	40,2	1319
18/08/2017	62,4	32,2	47,6	3	40,2	1319
21/08/2017	62,2	32,2	47,6	3	40,1	1316
28/08/2017	61,7	32,3	47,4	3	39,6	1303
07/09/2017	62,7	33,2	46,9	3	39,7	1310
12/09/2017	62,1	32	47,1	3	40,1	1319
14/09/2017	63	33,2	46,9	3	40	1316
19/09/2017	62,9	33,6	47,3	3	40,3	1326

Date	Abdomen (cm)	Waist (cm)	5 cm below belly button (cm)	Right thigh (cm)	Left thigh (cm)	Right arm (cm)	Left arm (cm)
01/08/2017	88	77	101	60	61	32	32
03/08/2017	84	76	99	61	59	33	32
08/08/2017	82	75	93	60	60	32	32

11/08/2017	80	75	90	59	60	31	31
15/08/2017	81	75	92	58	59	32	32
18/08/2017	81	74	91	58	59	32	32
21/08/2017	81	73	90	58	59	32	32
28/08/2017	81	72	89	58	59	32	32
07/09/2017	81	72	90	58	59	32	32
12/09/2017	80	73	89	58	58	32	32
14/09/2017	80	72	89	57	57	32	32
19/09/2017	80	72	89	57	57	32	32

Initial photos:

a)

b)

Figure 3 - Initial photos: a) frontal; b) left lateral

Final photos:

Figure 4 - Final photos: a) frontal; b) left lateral

Graphic 1 - Measurement of the abdomen throughout the sessions

Graphic 2 - Measurement of the thighs throughout the sessions

Conclusions

The patient presented at the initial consultation a weight of 63.1 kg and height of 160 cm, presenting a BMI of 24.6.

Figure 5 - Body Mass Index for the patient. Adapted from <http://www.smartbmiccalculator.com/result.html?unit=0&hc=160&wk=63%2C1&us=1&ua=26&ue=0&gk=>

This chart shows the patients BMI value and its age-dependent significance for the health. The value is marked in the center of the highlighted area.

According to the BMI chart, the patient (26) has normal weight for her height. After analyzing the percentage table of fat mass for females, it is in the "Healthy" range. (Figure 6)

Figure 6 - Body fat ranges for adults. Adapted from <http://www.goodmeasuremeals.com/products/tanita>

The results confirm that the patient lost volume, a fact that is noticed by the loss of centimeters in both the abdomen and the thighs (Graphic 1 and 2).

The BMI was not altered.

The patient confirms that she notices improvements in the cellulitis in the thigh area and that the skin is much smoother.

The lack of improvement results in the percentage of fat mass (initial: 30.9, final 33.6) is due to the fact that the patient confirmed that she did not follow the diet at 100% and did not exercise during the treatment.

These treatments help in reducing the body measurements, but it is also necessary to follow a good diet and practice exercise. The patient was advised to attend nutrition consultations and exercise to continue to reduce weight.

The role of diet in autoimmune diseases seems to be important, especially with regard to induction in some cases, but the true extent of its influence and the therapeutic potential are still largely unknown in this context.

Physical exercise is of equal importance to enhance the results that the treatments provide.

However, these two major reasons are not responsible alone for weight loss. If there is a hormonal imbalance, which many people with Hashimoto's Thyroiditis have, then it will be extremely difficult, if not impossible to lose a significant amount of weight by eating and exercising alone. Eating a lot of refined foods and skipping meals affects two of the major hormones in the body, cortisol and insulin. And when someone continues these habits for many years, this will put stress on the adrenal glands, and can eventually lead to insulin resistance. And until this is corrected, we can eat a perfect diet and exercise daily and it will be difficult to lose weight.

Many people with Hashimoto's Thyroiditis and other types of hypothyroidism also have an imbalance in the ratio between the hormones estrogen and progesterone, which can also lead to weight gain and thus make it difficult to lose weight. The patient was advised to consult with a competent natural endocrine doctor, as they will be able to detect a hormonal imbalance and if they determine she has one, help her correct it.

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